

English Language Skills and Employability Opportunities

Dr. Karandikar Vallabh Shankar

Assistant Professor, B. D. Kale Mahavidyalaya, Ghodegaon, Tal. Ambegaon, Dist. Pune

Corresponding Author – Dr. Karandikar Vallabh Shankar

DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.19510292

Abstract:

Language plays an important role in the human world. English is the global lingua franca. It rules the world as it is globally recognised and accepted as the language of intellectual makeup. As the language of technology, it has a great scope. All the important domains and fields use English as their functional language. It has accorded a global status to the English language. Therefore, English plays an important role in getting professional mobility. This global status of English provides innumerable opportunities for English users. Mastering the English language skills has become a gateway to employability. It is the platform that helps us reach our desired destination. The emergence of English offers employment opportunities in many important domains such as education, aviation, business, technology, and science. To meet the global employability demands, mastering English language skills has become a necessity. Mastering English language skills assists in personal and career development. It enhances global opportunities, providing employability options. It focuses on the bond between English language skills and employability opportunities.

Keywords: *Lingua Franca, Global Status, Professional Mobility, Employment Opportunities, Career Development.*

Introduction:

This paper highlights the importance and connection between English language skills and employability opportunities in the present contemporary world. Mastering the English language skills is the most important challenge for this generation. In all walks of life, English plays an important role. Without knowing English, it's rather difficult to participate and conduct meetings, conferences and interviews. Listening, speaking, reading and writing are the language skills that must be practiced and mastered for career growth and promotion. The technological developments in the 21st century provide numerous AI tools to master English language skills. To access information and gain knowledge of the world, English plays an important role. The recent AI platforms like ChatGPT, Deep Search, Grammarly, and Quill blot are some of the

important advanced tools that are very useful for grammar and spelling checks. These tools also give suggestions to modify the content, replacing suitable and appropriate words. There are many useful chatbots and tools for communication practice. This paper highlights important domains that provide employability opportunities if we master the English language skills.

Objectives:

This paper aims to highlight the role of English in getting employability opportunities in the global market. Therefore, the following are objectives:

1. To examine the importance of the English language skills.
2. To study the bond between English language skills and employability opportunities.
3. To highlight important domains that

provide employment opportunities to English learners.

4. To understand the present Indian scenario and future employability opportunities.

The Role of English in the 21st Century:

Understanding and mastering the English language skills are necessary in the 21st century. Knowledge of English is a must to access the information worldwide. English is the language of networking. Meetings, conferences, presentations, interviews, and negotiations take place in English throughout the world. Therefore, understanding modern English usage is important. Those who master English pronunciation, vocabulary, tone, accent, and grammar have scope in this modern, advanced and tech-savvy world. The importance of English in IT, media, business, marketing and global industries has maximized the career opportunities and employability. The technological advancements and online digital processes have made tremendous changes in society. Computer literacy has become the top priority in this advanced world. Without understanding English, it is difficult excel in the IT world.

IT and Technology:

English is the language of IT and Technology. Coding and programming are important domains of the IT world. The language programmes are in English, and for global collaboration, communication and documentation, English is widely used. To access AI tools, English plays an important role. English assists in understanding technology. Those who master the English language skills can navigate and master global technology. Therefore, English language learners have great scope in IT.

Social Media:

The importance of social media is

increasing day by day. It provides employability opportunities to English language learners throughout the world. Digital content creation has gained importance. There are many new career paths that have emerged, such as content creator, media manager, social media analyst, influencer, etc. The use of English in social media content provides global employability opportunities. There are countless English videos on YouTube, which assist to know the functions of AI tools, but without knowledge of English, it is difficult to understand and access these tools.

Business:

English is the global language of business. Multinational companies use English as the language of their trade and business. English is used to record all business documents, such as meetings, reports and transactions. Digital technology plays a vital role in business development. All the technological documentation is prepared in English. English helps strengthen business relationships and smooth negotiations. Proficiency in English helps to increase business credibility and strengthen collaborative work. English plays a crucial role in business process outsourcing. English is used for customer support services to solve the problems and queries of the customers through emails and telephonic conversations. The proficient user of English understands cultural differences through varieties of English and can satisfy the customers through his accent and polite tone. In recruitment and training, English has given the topmost priority for enhancing communication. It shows that the ability to understand tone and the variety of English enhances understanding and helps in finding the appropriate solutions. Therefore, those who are excellent communicators and use English fluently have better employment opportunities.

Travel and Tourism:

Guiding tourists and travelling across the world is an interesting business. Everyone loves to travel and visit different destinations. English helps to gain information about the different tourist places in the world. English manners and etiquette play an important role in satisfying the travellers' needs. Customer satisfaction always enhances the business. Understanding the needs of the customers and providing expected services is the main motto of the travel and tourism business. English communication skills, use of appropriate terminology, manners and etiquette play a very important role. There is great scope for tourist guides and travel agents who can speak English correctly and confidently, using polite language and appropriate expressions in English.

Content Writing:

It is an important domain that provides employment opportunities to English users who can create content effectively. Content writing is a kind of writing that performs various roles like persuading, educating, informing and entertaining the audience. The English language learners have a great scope in content writing. Quality content and effective writing skills are needed in content writing. Writing perfection and the ability to compose effective short messages are the most needed aspects of content writing. There is a need for translators and content writers for effective functioning, and therefore, there is a demand for such experts who can do this job effectively.

Marketing and Advertising:

Marketing and advertising are important factors of business development. English plays an important role in the audio-visual creation of advertising and marketing. The impactful advertising and marketing strategies decide the business growth and future. Therefore,

appropriate resources are hired to maintain quality. English advertising expands the business across the world. Creative content creators and fluent and effective communicators always get priority. An excellent and brief message, appropriate and effective vocabulary and tone, voice modulation, accent and overall impact of the English speaker decide the quality and impact of advertising. Those who imagine and think well in English and can compose effective, beautiful and creative novel messages are always given top priority. It shows that using the English language effectively is a skill, and those who master it get employment opportunities.

Hospitality and Customer Services:

An effective communicator who masters all the English language skills has a great scope in today's world. Listening to customers patiently and responding to them politely, understanding their problems and psychology, is a challenging job. Language plays a unique role in capturing human thoughts. Language is an instrument of thought, and therefore, it should be used with certain care. Using appropriate diction and tone helps for smooth functioning and to avoid conflicts. Therefore, there is always a great demand for such people, who are excellent communicators, who can provide hospitality and take care of customers by understanding, supporting and solving their problems satisfactorily.

Availability of Sources for Mastering English Language Skills:

In this world of technological advancement, ample resources are available for learning and mastering the English language skills. The availability of digital platforms has made English learning easy and entertaining. Websites, software, AI tools, mobile apps, e-content and countless digital platforms are

available to master English language skills. English grammar, vocabulary, tone, accent, intonation pattern, listening and talking practices are easily available and accessible for learners to learn and master English to get employment opportunities throughout the world. Online evaluation, assignments, and observations promote the learning of English and make the learning process smooth, effective and interesting.

The Recent Indian Scenario and Future:

India is a developing nation, and the government is planning and implementing effective strategies for national development. The new education policy of the government lays emphasis on the use of technology by promoting the use of ICT in the teaching and learning process. India is making large investments in IT, infrastructure and industry to promote business and to provide employment opportunities. It shows that there will be a great scope in future to be more prosperous. *Viksit Bharat 2047* is the vision of India to transform India as a developed nation. The key pillars of this vision are: digital transformation, modern infrastructure, and inclusive growth. It shows that India will prosper in future, providing more employment opportunities to English language learners.

In India, there is a great demand for English learners. The government is also promoting new avenues of learning. Extensive use of ICT has given priority to enhancing the learning process with better tools and methods widely used around the globe. The emergence of online services has indirectly promoted the use of English and created employment opportunities. Many agencies and placement services are conducting training and internship programmes to help students understand English language skills and other soft skills to provide employment opportunities. Effective English communication skills need to be learned, practiced and mastered

for the smooth functioning of the global activities.

Major findings:

1. Mastering English language skills has a scope in the global market.
2. English communication skills provide employment opportunities.
3. English language skills enhance the understanding and help to perform better.
4. The future predicts employment opportunities for those who will master English.

Conclusion:

English is an important international language that is widely used across the world. Understanding English is necessary to get connected with the world and to access information about the world. To get global access and to expand our business, mastering English is necessary. The business forums in the world use English to expand their business. English is the language of important sectors such as business, trade, transportation, education, science, IT, technology, law, aviation, media, marketing, advertising, and freelancing. All these sectors use English to be globally accessible. It shows that to excel in these domains and to get employability opportunities throughout the world, the English language plays an important role. AI plays a very crucial role in learning English, but the language of AI is also English, and a few learners find it difficult to understand all the functions of digital tools due to a low understanding of English. But it is clear that without studying, understanding and mastering English and its sub-skills, it is difficult to get employability opportunities in the domains where English is used, and English users have been given top priority.

Reference:

1. Banerjee A.K.(2007). *New Directions in Grammar and English Language Teaching*.

- Pointer Publishers
2. Carol, J. C., & Burnum, M. (1991). *The official guide to modern English usage* (2nd ed.). MJF Books.
 3. Dash Meena & Dash M.T. (2007). *Teaching English as an Additional Language*. Atlantic Publishers
 4. Crystal, D. (2010). *The Cambridge encyclopedia of language*. Cambridge University Press.
 5. Nagraj Geetha (2005) *English Language Teaching: Approaches, Methods, Techniques* Orient Longman
 6. Schofield, J., & Osborn, A. (2016). *English for business speaking*. HarperCollins Publishers.